

The Place of African Traditional Medicine, Magic and Digital Economy

Michael Ibrahim Bazai

Department of Religious Studies, Kaduna State University, Kaduna, Nigeria

Abstract

In most African societies, traditional medicine plays an important role in the lives of millions who cannot access western medicine while digital economy is rapidly changing the way we humans behave in all aspects of the society which includes magic and health-care. Since the dawn of consciousness, man has been confronted with a sense of need with which he knows that his own unaided power cannot cope. The complications and riddles of life have been such as urge upon him the need for succor, for deliverance and for mastery over environmental circumstances. As such, mankind uses some powers or means to help him or her solve some problems beyond his control and at the same time for his own personal needs. Communities experience this power as useful and therefore helpful, acceptable or neutral, or harmful and evil. This paper examines the place of African Traditional Medicine, Magic and Digital Economy. Although the paper focuses more on Nigeria but references are drawn around Africa and the world at large to buttress the growing demand for traditional medicine, Magic and Digital Economy. The paper concludes that African Traditional Medicine, Magic and Digital Economy are mutually connected and beneficial to each other and the belief and practices in them arose as a result of man's quest to satisfy his needs. The practice of all these is still deeply rooted in many African societies especially in Nigeria, regardless of education, religion, and social class of the people concerned.

Keywords: African Traditional Medicine, Magic and Digital Economy

Introduction

Aristotle, a Greek philosopher and scientist, one of the greatest intellectual figures of Western history said “Man is by nature a social animal; an individual who is unsocial naturally and not accidentally is either beneath our notice or more than human. Society is something that precedes the individual. Anyone who either cannot lead the common life or is so self-sufficient as not to need to, and therefore does not partake of society, is either a beast or a god.” It means that the human person is a social being who lives and works together with other human beings in his or her search for the basic necessities of life. In living and working with others, human beings meet with complicated situations or encounter problems that need serious attention.

The complications and riddles of life have been such as urge upon him the need for succor, for deliverance and for mastery over environmental circumstances. As such mankind uses some powers or means to help him or her solve some problems beyond his control and at the same time for his own personal needs. Access to this power is hierarchical-it comes from God through the spirits and living dead to some human beings; communities experience this power as useful and therefore helpful, acceptable or neutral, or harmful and evil. Some of the ways to access this power for good or for evil is through the use of African traditional medicine, magic and digital economy. Africans in spite of their commitment to Christianity or Islam, still feel not secure in their personal, physical, health and property safety. They tent to use other means that they feel would help them satisfy their different needs. Thus, this study will discuss the meaning, use, effect and the relationship between African traditional medicines, magic and digital economy and how they are used to solve or satisfy human needs.

Clarification of Key Terms

1. African Traditional Medicine

World Health Organization (WHO) defines traditional medicine as the sum total of the knowledge, skills, and practices based on the theories, beliefs, and experiences indigenous to different cultures, whether explicable or

not, used in the maintenance of health as well as in the prevention, diagnosis, improvement or treatment of physical and mental illness.¹ African Traditional Medicine or Traditional African Medicine is a traditional medicine discipline involving indigenous herbalism and African spirituality, typically involving diviners, midwives, and herbalists. African Traditional Medicine has its roots in every culture around Africa. There are many different systems of traditional medicine and the philosophy and practices of each are influenced by social conditions, environment and geographic location, but these systems all agree on a holistic approach to life.² In other words, since the act of practicing traditional medicine is not digitalized, there are no scientific methods of diagnosis, the health care services provided by the healers are based on culture, religious background, knowledge attitudes, and their community beliefs. By using traditional medicine, people can thrive and focus on their overall conditions, rather than on a particular ailment that typically arises from a lack of equilibrium of the mind, body and environment. It involves the medicinal use of plants or plant extracts that may be eaten or applied to the skin to treat disease and enhance general health and wellbeing.

An African traditional practitioner or healer is one who provides medical care in the community that he lives; using herbs, minerals, animal parts, incantations, and other methods, based on the cultures and beliefs of his people.³ This healer or practitioner must be seen to be competent, versatile, experienced and trusted. While according to Mbiti as cited in Kanu, African medical practitioners refers to the friends, pastors, psychiatrists and doctors of African traditional societies who have a language, symbolism, knowledge and skill of their own to combat or cure sickness or disease.⁴ They are the doctors and pastors of the sick. According to Quarcoopome, they are called traditional doctors, traditional healers or herbalists, because they have power and control over herbs.⁵ The African traditional medicine practitioners are called *Bokaye* in Hausa, *Dibia* in Igbo *Babalawos* in Yoruba and *Waganga* in Swahili.

Also, they principally concern themselves with sickness, disease and misfortune. They symbolize the hope of society: hopes of good health, security and prosperity. In African traditional societies, sickness, disease and misfortune are generally believed to be caused by the ill will or ill action of one person against the other. The medical personnel is consulted to diagnose the type of sickness and trace the cause of it. The satisfactory answer that people need at a time when the question of the cause is sought is that 'someone' caused it. Even if it is a mosquito bite, someone must have sent the mosquito. As a solution to the problem in question, the cause must be found, counteracted, uprooted and punished. It is also the duty of the medical practitioner to provide countermeasures that can counteract future inflictions. Practitioners of traditional African medicine claim to be able to cure various and diverse conditions such as cancers, psychiatric disorders, high blood pressure, cholera, most venereal diseases, epilepsy, asthma, eczema, fever, anxiety, depression, benign prostatic hyperplasia, urinary tract infections, gout, and healing of wounds and burns. The traditional medicine men typically involve diviners, midwives, and herbalists.

Kanu, identifies eight types of medical practitioners:⁶

1. The general practitioners;
2. The herbalist (specializes in herbal application) and native doctors (inclined to supernatural powers);
3. Faith healers (here patients are forced to confess their sins, ones done they become emotionally healed);
4. Bone setters;
5. The native gynecologist and midwife;
6. The witchdoctor who specializes in witch/wizard-caused diseases, most of them being formally wizards and witches;
7. The blood letter (the use of horn or other means to let bad blood out of the body);
8. Traditional surgeon;

The Positive Effects of African Traditional Medicine

There are some advantages in using African Traditional Medicine. Sam⁷highlighted some as:

1. They cost less: The rising cost of prescriptive drugs have led some people to look for alternatives. While medicinal herbs may not be as strong or as fast acting as conventional medicine, there is a growing body of scientific evidence that shows their efficacy and in what those.
2. **They may have fewer side effects:** While the side effects of any herbal medication depend on the drug in question, many have fewer side effects than conventional medicine.
3. **There is a choice on how to use them:** Medicinal herbs can be used in a variety of ways, depending on the kind of herb that is to be used. Some herbs can be mixed with food. Some can be made into tea, and there are some that are available in capsule or tablet form.
4. **They are good for more than one condition:** Most prescriptive drugs are designed for one specific health problem. By contrast, many herbal medicines act on several parts of the body at once.
5. **Other purposes:** African Traditional Medicine is not only for sickness or any disability, but also for good luck, security of lives and property, and warding off of any imminent evil or demonic attacks.

The Negative Effects of African Traditional Medicine

Herbs are not without disadvantages, and herbal medicine is not appropriate in all situations. The following are some of its negative effects:

1. Lack of dosage instructions and regulation. There is the very real risks of doing oneself harm through self-dosing with herbs. While one can argue that the same thing can happen with medications, such as accidentally overdosing on cold remedies, many herbs do not come with instructions or package inserts. As such, there's a very real risk of overdose. Also, because herbal products are not tightly regulated, consumers also run the risk of buying inferior quality herbs. The quality of herbal products may vary among batches, brands or manufacturers. This can make it much more difficult to prescribe the proper dose of an herb.
2. Inappropriate use of traditional medicines or practices can have negative or dangerous effects on one's health and or life in general.
3. There is poor or slow transition of knowledge and practice of African Traditional Medicine. This is because it is considered as a hidden treasure or knowledge that will pass from father to his only one beloved son of that family. In some cases when the main experts are no more in existence, the practice of that traditional medicine would cease to exist.
4. It lacks in-depth scientific validation and documentation. There are very little scientific studies/researches performed on actual efficacy, side effects and versatile nature of uses of many herbs. Consequently, no proper documentation.
5. Some of the African Traditional Medicine practitioners are not literate. They may not be able to have access to or utilize the digital media channels like internet, YouTube, Twitter, etc. This is a minus in terms of advertising their products and in the effectiveness of their work in terms of treating their patients or administering herbs.

Magic

Etymologically, according to the *New Encyclopedia Britannica*, the root word for *magic* (Greek: *mageia*; Latin: *magia*) was derived from the Greek term *magoi*, which refers to a Median tribe in Persia and their religion, Zoroastrianism.⁸ The Greco-Roman tradition held that magicians possessed arcane or secret knowledge and the ability to channel power from or through any of the polytheistic deities, spirits, or ancestors of the ancient pantheons. Magic has been defined by different scholars in different ways. Andrew defines it as “an attempt by man to tap and control the supernatural powers or resources of the universe for his own benefit. Its motto is, my will be done.”⁹ Similarly, Idowu¹⁰ describes magic as ‘an attempt on the part of man to tap and control the supernatural resources of the universe for his own benefit. In magic man commands the supernatural.

Magic refers to a ritual performance or activity that is thought to lead to the influencing of human or natural events by an external and interpersonal mystical power beyond the ordinary human sphere¹¹. For instance, mystical power may cause people to walk on fire, lie on thorns or nails, send curses or harm including death from a distance. Practitioners can also change into animals, spit on snakes and cause them to split open and die or stupefy thieves so that they are caught red-handed. They can convert inanimate objects into biologically active living creatures, or enable experts to delve deep to reveal hidden information, or reveal the future, or detect thieves and other culprits. This is why they wear charms, take medicines or get them rubbed into their bodies. They use experts such as diviners, or medicine men, to counteract the evil effects of this power, or obtain power charged objects containing the same power.

Thus, human beings cannot comprehend exactly how this power operates. The ‘interpersonal mystical power’ implies that human beings would be able to tap and manipulate this force for their benefit, and at the same time some people can use it to harm others. Magic can be used in different ways depending on the intention of the user. Thus, magic can be used for good and for evil (good magic and evil/bad magic) as Mbiti and Andrew observed¹². In this regard, good magic entails tapping and employing this force for the benefit of the society or community, while evil magic involves tapping and manipulating this power to harm other people and their property which is employed by witches, sorcerers and evil magicians as Richard explained further¹³.

In magic, there is a great dependence on incantation, deep breathing, fasting, worship, sacrifices etc. which speaks on a strong connection between magic and religion. However, magic differs from religion in the sense that its instrument of operation is manipulation rather than supplication without any address to the Supreme Being in a spirit of submission and appeal; it is not emotional and operates on professional-client relationship. Just like in the case of divination, magic is an important practice in witchcraft.¹⁴

It is very important to note that magic powers are exercised in Africa. Africans express their magic through words, especially from a senior to a junior in age, social status or position in the office.¹⁵ For instance, the words of a parent to children carry a lot of power, either for causing good fortune, curses, success, peace or sorrows. This is true when we reflect on these African proverbs that says “The strength of the elderly is in the ears and on the lips”. Also, “The mouth of an elderly man is without teeth, but never without words of wisdom”. Again, “The words of the elders do not lock all the doors; they leave the right door open”. Formal curses and blessings are extremely potent. People travel long distances to receive formal blessings, and conversely, they take extra care to avoid formal curses. Magical powers can be possessed through inheritance or apprenticeship. They can sometimes also be bought or sold. More so, the magicians both in the preparation and performance of a rite may need to be aware of a complex set of rules and regulations that may influence the efficacy and safety of the magic. It is worth to note that in preparation for magic, so many things can be used ranging from animal and plant objects to other inanimate objects such as skulls, skins, bones, dried bats, lizards, porcupine quills, leaves, stones, irons and sand. These things are believed to have occult powers that can be used to achieve man’s ends. One thing that is clear in magic is the belief that a spiritual power or some spiritual powers can be harnessed for good cause or otherwise of man and society. In a nutshell, magic is the manipulation of an external power by mechanical or behavioral means to affect others.

The Positive Effects of Magic

Magic can be used for good in different ways depending on the intention of the user.

1. Magic is used in the treatment of diseases,
2. Magic is used for protection against the evil forces that are found everywhere for instance in counteracting misfortunes, in warding off evil spirits and in diluting or destroying witchcraft. This is why some people wear or use charms, amulets, herbs, seeds, powder, skins, feathers, chanting of magical formula, cuts on the body and other magical practices so as to protect people and their property from evil power¹⁶

3. It can be used in marriage, farming and hunting, in lawsuits, in competitions, in seeking appointments, in making advances to women, in trading and even in examinations. As a result, most people usually wear rings and amulets; leather girdles/charm belts and other magical objects.
4. Religious specialists including diviners, medicine men, rain makers and others tap, manipulate and employ mystical power positively for the welfare of the community. For instance it is good magic that is used by the rain makers to bring rain and the diviners, seers and prophets use it to foretell the future.

The Negative Effects of Magic

1. Magic can be a cause of problems to a living body. Whenever there is drawn power from somewhere else to overpower a corporeal (or even incorporeal) entity, it will easily affect the body during the effect of the magical procedure and sometimes even beyond.
2. Magic can cause misfortune and make life uncomfortable.
3. Detracting minds of people

Digital Economy

Digital economy, also known as the Internet economy, new economy, or the Web economy, refers to the worldwide network of economic activities, commercial transactions and professional interactions that are enabled by information and communications technologies¹⁷. Digital economy can also be defined as economic activities that emerge from connecting individuals, businesses, devices, data and operations through digital technology. It encompasses the online connections and transactions that take place across multiple sectors and technologies, such as the internet, mobile technology, big data and information and communications technology. Simply put, it is the economy based on digital technologies¹⁸ or economic value derived from the internet.

The digital economy is characterized by the digitations of many products and services and the use of the Internet and other networks as stated above to support economic activities. The traditional marketplace shifts to a virtual market space. It is worth to note then that competition in such an environment is very intense and major changes occur. The impact of digital economy on business can be identified at three basic levels: improving direct marketing, transforming organizations, and redefining organizations. The digital economy differs from a traditional economy because of its reliance on digital technology, online transactions and its transformative effect on traditional industries. Digital innovations such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), virtual reality, blockchain and autonomous vehicles all play a part in creating a digital economy.¹⁹

The digital economy is a recently-emerging phenomenon of increasing importance given estimates of double-digit annual growth around the world, with particularly strong growth in the global South (WEF 2015). The driving forces behind this emergence are economic and political, but they of course also have roots in technological innovation (itself shaped by wider forces)

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No wonder in its earliest days, the digital economy was sometimes called the internet economy, the new economy or the web economy because of its reliance on internet connectivity. However, economists and business leaders assert that the digital economy is more advanced and complex than the internet economy. The digital economy reflects the move from the third industrial revolution to the fourth industrial revolution. The third industrial revolution -- sometimes called the *digital revolution* -- refers to the changes that took place in the late 20th century with the transition from analog electronic and mechanical devices to digital technologies. The fourth industrial revolution builds on the digital revolution as technologies today continue to bridge the physical world and cyber world.

Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated digital economic growth as remote work, online shopping, telemedicine and digital entertainment became essential during lockdowns and social distancing. The digital economy continues to evolve and expand rapidly, with emerging technologies and innovations shaping its trajectory. There has been significant development since the inception of digital economy. We have so many examples of traditional companies transforming to succeed in the digital economy. Below are notable ones:

- i. **Inception of digital trade and e-commerce:** The surge of e-commerce -- where platforms such as Amazon, Alibaba and eBay have transformed online buying and selling -- has reshaped retail and created new technologies and business models.
- ii. **Social media:** The emergence of social networking platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WhatsApp and LinkedIn has changed how people communicate, connect and promote their products.
- iii. **Digital payments and crypto currencies:** Digital payment systems such as Pampay, POS, Venmo and mobile wallets have changed how people conduct financial transactions.
- iv. **Omni-channel approach to sales.** Many retailers reach and serve customers through multiple channels such as online sales and mobile apps. This lets them identify buyers, whether they're shopping via the internet or in person. They can collect and analyze each customer's browsing and sales data to better understand their interests and use that data to reach out to customers via social media, enabling better service and ultimately higher sales and increased brand loyalty.
- v. **Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Automation.** These have significantly shaped the digital economy in different countries especially African countries. Virtual assistants, chatbots and recommendation algorithms powered by AI improve consumer experiences and provide more personalized services.
- vi. **Digital entertainment.** The entertainment industry has undergone significant changes due to the rise of streaming services such as Netflix, Spotify and YouTube. These platforms have revolutionized media consumption by providing instant access to an array of content.
- vii. **Telemedicine.** The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the spread of telemedicine and made remote medical care possible through digital platforms.
- viii. **Increased remote work adoption.** There is this African adage that says when one is hungry one would surely discover his or her talent. The COVID 19 pandemic caused a change in workplace culture. This is because more people accepted remote work and began using apps such as Zoom, Slack and Microsoft Teams to promote online collaboration especially to transact business or hold meetings. The use of cooking gas to power generators which replaces the normal petrol in most places in Nigeria is another example. The digital economy has evolved as a result of this trend, which has reshaped how businesses function and manage their workforce.

- ix. **Sharing economy.** The sharing economy has transformed how people share resources such as cars, lodging and services, as exemplified by the Uber. Many people in Nigeria for instance these days while traveling prefer to use commercial bus or travel in group using one vehicle instead of their private vehicles because of increase in fuel pump price. The digital economy is expanding rapidly with the use of new technologies that improve connectivity, enable automation, advance data analysis and create new business prospects. Common technologies that are accelerating the digital economy include the following:
- a. **5G:** 5G technology enables rapid downloads, low latency and a wide range of device connections. 5G offers many advantages, including facilitating smooth data transfers, enhancing mobile experiences and fostering the development of innovative applications and services.
 - b. **Wi-Fi 6:** In comparison to earlier Wi-Fi (**Wireless Fidelity**) standards, Wi-Fi 6, also known as 802.11ax, provides faster data transfer rates, decreased latency and increased network efficiency. It also accommodates the increasing number of connected devices and the demand for high-bandwidth applications, making connections faster and more dependable, especially in congested areas.
 - c. **Augmented Reality and Virtual Reality:** Augmented reality and virtual reality technologies are revolutionizing gaming, education, healthcare and training through the development of immersive experiences and simulations.
 - d. **Artificial Intelligence (AI).** AI technologies, including generative AI, machine learning and natural language processing, facilitate automation, data analysis and decision-making for organizations across various industries. Businesses can analyze large amounts of data, improve customer experiences, automate activities and increase operational efficiency with the help of AI-powered systems.
 - e. **Blockchain:** Blockchain technology enables decentralized and secure recording and verification of transactions. It eliminates the need for intermediaries and secures the transparency, immutability and trustworthiness of digital transactions. This technology is transforming Industries, including finance, supply chain management and healthcare.
 - f. **Internet of Things (IoT):** IoT is a system of networked sensors and devices used for data collection and exchange. By enabling the fusion of physical items with the digital world, this technology creates new possibilities for automation, real-time monitoring and data-driven insights. Smart homes, smart cities, agriculture and industrial automation are just a few of the areas where IoT applications are improving efficiency, productivity and convenience.
 - g. **Quantum computing.** While still in its early stages, quantum computing can tackle difficult problems at previously unheard-of speeds. It has applications in cryptography, materials science and optimization.

The Positive Effects of Digital Economy

1. The ease of global interconnection enables businesses to reach new markets and better maintain the customers they have.
2. Using data and analytics, businesses are able to make more informed decisions about the product they offer, and formulate marketing strategies targeted perfectly at specific consumers.
3. In a web economy, networked intelligence has enabled companies to ramp up the competition by being more aware of what consumers want and allowing them more choices.
4. With today's prevalence of a work-from-anywhere-culture, employees through digital economy have come to expect the same level of connectivity as they had in a physical office.
5. The global economy is experiencing massive, accelerated digital transformation, resulting in the creation of new business models, innovative products and services, and very different ways of doing business.
6. Smartphone apps have encouraged the growth of the internet economy. Goods and services are being delivered via online platforms. Consumer spending is increasingly driving towards online sales. Digital IT solutions are replacing hardware. And data has become a valuable currency in this new digital age.

7. Digital economy has helped enterprises improved their competitiveness, optimized resources, and transformed traditional models, enhanced efficiency and financial health.
8. The internet has enabled consumers to have greater information and choice. For example, it makes it easier to compare prices between firms. It also brings information to a person's fingertips.
9. Digital economy saves business labour costs **and time**. Before if you needed office supplies, you would have to make a journey into town and purchase. Now, you can make an order over the internet and it will arrive the next day.
10. A digital economy allows greater personalisation than would be possible under traditional economy. For example, a traditional shop would only have room to stock a certain number of colours and sizes, but with the digital economy, a consumer can choose any preference and then the product can be custom-built e.g. 3D printer. For example, custom clothes that have particular sizes and colours to match individual preferences.

Negative Effects of Digital Economy

1. Despite the potential for new start-ups, many aspects of the digital economy have become dominated by firms with monopoly power. For instance Google and Facebook have all developed very strong brand loyalty and market share in their respective markets. This has made a few tech giants very profitable. With monopoly power, Google are able to charge high prices for online advertising
2. With the digital alternative undercutting traditional firms, old fashioned bookshops which were sources of interaction and socialisation have been forced out of business. Although books may be cheaper, there is less community interaction because we have lost physical interaction between sellers and buyers which was an important aspect of the buying experience.
3. Digital economy increases the rate of crime and terrorism. This is because technology provides new ways for criminals to operate. The internet in particular provides opportunities for malevolent forces to exploit. Examples of this include terrorists using social media to promote themselves and encourage others; scammers hack into people's account to steal their money; drug dealers using the dark web to trade; pedophiles using chat rooms and other places to groom potential victims, exchange photos, videos and other information; and authoritarian regimes attempting to sway or distort elections in democratic countries.
4. The digital economy has enabled the proliferation of content that is damaging to human well-being.
5. The pace of digitalisation an actually lead to structural unemployment or increase in inequality in society. This is because of some unskilled workers increasingly losing out to skilled workers and combined with the monopoly power of big tech firms.
6. Many companies and industries that didn't or couldn't capitalize on the technologies to change their operations have faced declining sales, falling market share and even complete collapse. For example, Blockbuster and other content rental shops that didn't adopt streaming technologies quickly enough shuttered their operations. The taxi industry is also another example, as it struggles to compete for customers who find Uber and Lyft easier to use.
7. The existence of a digital divide which refers to the disparity between those who have access to technology and those who don't, is a major weakness of the digital economy. This division can result in inequalities concerning access to information, education, employment prospects and economic advancement.

The Connection between African Traditional Medicine, Magic and Digital Economy

African Traditional Medicine, Magic and Digital Economy are mutually connected and beneficiary to each other in so many ways. They are connected through advert online and television channels. The magicians and medicine men use the digital media channels to make known the quality, integrity and intensity of their products. This is evident in most of the Ghanaian TV channels where many use them as means of advert. Through that they

get customers; and they use the customers' practical experiences of their products. In other words, their testimonies or benefits are returned to the same online channels or TV to testify. By so doing, viewers generate money to the media channels which enhance digital economy. Both African Traditional Medicine, Magic and Digital Economy have a common root-both arose as a result of man's quest to satisfy his needs. They are therefore an attempt by man as Andrew pointed out to deal with the mystery that surrounds his immediate physical environment.²¹

Digital economy highlights the opportunity and the need for organizations and individuals to use technologies to execute existing tasks on the computer better, faster and often differently than before. Such opportunities for existing entities to do better, to do more, to do things differently and to do new things is encompassed in the related concept of digital transformation. This has made it easier also for people to know and get access to the traditional medical doctors and magicians through the use of the digital media channels. This is because as earlier noted above, the magicians and medicine men use the digital media channels to make known the quality, integrity and intensity of their products.

In a similar vein, digital economy which has to do with digital networking and communication infrastructures provide a global platform to interact, communicate, collaborate and search for information. Magic men and traditional medicine men uses the digital technology or media channels to make known their contacts by giving of their phone numbers and other description that their clients can use to reach them easily and faster. This can be seen displayed clearly on the TV screen, YouTube channel and other media channels. This also in a way has enhanced or creates opportunities to transcend the barriers of time and space whereby information and or business can be carried out within a short period and at different places.

It is worth to notes that despite their relatedness, they differ in so many ways and areas. There is the distrust in anything African or Nigerian. With the advent of western culture into Africa, there is the distrust of anything African. During the slave trade and later colonialism as Kanu observed²² the colonial masters gave the blacks the impression that they were a superior race. In French colonies through the principle of "assimilation", they tried to stop the indigenous language of colonies which they considered inferior to the French language. In a similar vein in British colonies, English was taught in schools. Many Africans have grown with the impression that their language, culture and other aspects of live are inferior. Many Africans see their traditional mode of dressing, songs and dances, traditional medicine, marriage etc. as archaic, evil pagan. This made many people to view anybody using or practicing African Traditional medicine and or magic as evil and bad. This affects it in terms of practice or patronage. Whereas digital economy is seen as good as such people openly and freely use the digital media channels without any fair or shame.

Traditional African Medicine and magic still has not been documented and under process of documentation as from generations to generations, this was hidden as secret concept of healing. This is considered as a hidden treasure or knowledge that will pass from father to his only one beloved son of that family. There are various healing concepts in Traditional African Medicine (TAM) which includes herbalism, surgery, bone setting, spinal manipulation, etc. However, lack of in-depth scientific validation of these African traditional medicines and their documentation is a greatest lacuna because it creates room for Europeans who encountered Africa earlier to misunderstand their practices as pagan; it is therefore not surprising that African medical practitioners suffered much in their hands and more so in the hands of European-American writers and missionaries who often called them witch-doctors, alongside other derogatory names. But in the digital economy palace, the materials or relevant information are well documented and made available in the various digital media channels for interested individuals, organizations or communities to have access to them. More so, people are trained always on how to use them. But the only problem is that with Urbanization and Industrialization, many have left African Villages for the cities. This has seriously affected the practice of African Traditional Medicine and Magic. This is not in any way to say that African Traditional Medicine and Magic has died; the African concept of life as *summum bonum* (the highest good) and the struggle to preserve it still creates enough appetite

for African Traditional Medicine and Magic. It is therefore not surprising that men and women who are preparing to get married very often bring the pictures of the person they intend to marry for a pastor to tell them if it is their right partner.

Conclusion

African traditional medicine, magic and digital economy are mutually connected and beneficial to each other as explained in the paper. And the belief and practices in them arose as a result of man's quest to satisfy his needs. They deal with the mystery that surrounds man's immediate physical environment. The practice of all these is still deeply rooted in many African societies especially in Nigeria, regardless of education, religion, and social class of the people concerned. According to many Africans, Nigerians in particular, its incidence is even increasing due to social stress and strain caused (among others) by the process of modernization.

The paper shows African traditional medicine, magic and digital economy are used for both good and evil by people depending on the user. They can be used for the benefit or destruction of an individual or community. The paper encouraged the positive use of them for the betterment of mankind. That is to say the practice and use of African traditional medicine, magic and digital media channels are permissible in Nigeria so long as they are not used for socially disapproved goals.

Recommendations

In the light of our discourse, the paper makes the following recommendations towards enhancing African traditional medicine, magic and digital economy:

1. The paper recommends the Federal Government of Nigeria to try and enhance the digital technology and media channels. The internet service is poor. There are so many parts of the country that there is poor internet service. Government should enhance digital technology and channels through services and power it.
2. The Federal Government of Nigeria should try and checkmate digital manipulation by taking cyber security measures to address increasingly sophisticated cyber threats, including AI-powered attacks. By applying machine learning algorithms, AI-powered, cyber security systems so as to detect abnormal behavior in digital technology and of traditional medicine men and magicians, identify potential vulnerabilities and proactively lower the risk factors.
3. There should be implementation and enforcement of strong anti-cybercrime policies which will seek to not only reduce crimes or abnormal behaviours by African traditional medicine men, Magic men and digital technology or media channels, but also find and prosecute offenders.
4. To those in the area of African traditional medicine, magic and digital economy media or channels, they should not be seen using them as a source of destruction but help in bringing development to individuals and communities.
5. To Africans, Nigerians in particular, African traditional medicine and magic should not be considered as evil; rather they should see what good they can make out of them.
6. Africans, Nigerians to be specific should accept, use and encourage "African made technologies and medicines," which will encourage more production and consumption by Africans.

Endnotes

¹World Health Organization (WHO) "Traditional Medicine Definition" Last Modified June, 2008. <https://www.who.int/medicines/areas/traditional/definitions/en/.htm>

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